

The authors earlier reported the gravimetric estimation of niobium using the reagent in aqueous media⁸. No reference has been found in literature regarding the use of this reagent in electrometric methods.

Experimental

E.M.F. measurements were made with a digital pH meter (ECL Model PH 5651) having a single glass-calomel electrode assembly.

Preparation of niobium solution: Requisite quantity of niobium pentachloride (Fluka) was dissolved in absolute alcohol. Care was taken to avoid moisture while weighing.

Preparation of the reagent: The reagent was prepared by the described method⁴. The compound is fine white needles, m. p. 259° and is soluble in water and warm alcohol.

MPTTPT was dissolved in slightly warm absolute alcohol. The strength of the reagent solution was kept the same as that of the niobium pentachloride solution.

5 ml of niobium pentachloride solution was taken in the cell every time and the titrant (MPTTPT reagent) solution added from a microburette. Direct and reverse titrations were performed. Several such experiments were performed using 0.01M, 0.005M and 0.004M solutions of niobium pentachloride. In all the titrations, sharp change was noticed at the equivalence point after which the potential became steady again. The end-point was obtained from the maximum of $\Delta E/\Delta V$ and corresponds to 1:1 complex.

It is noteworthy that tantalum does not interfere in the estimation of niobium by this method. The method described above is rapid and accurate for the estimation of such compounds of niobium which get hydrolysed in aqueous media but are soluble in absolute alcohol.

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 347.
2. J. V. DUSKY and J. TRTILEK, *Chem. Obzor.*, 1934, 9, 203; *Chem. Abs.*, 1935, 29, 2876.
3. PUSHPA SHARDA and G. C. SHIVAHARE, Paper presented at the session of the Indian Science Congress Association, 1980.
4. M. BUSCH, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2510.

Determination of Equilibrium Constant of Ferric Formate Complex by Paper Electrophoresis

H. G. MUKHERJEE* and (Miss) ALOKA DEBI

Pure Chemistry Department, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 25 September 1980, revised 8 September 1981, accepted 11 March 1982

PAPER electrophoresis has been applied to the study of metal complexes in solution. Attempts have also been made to determine the stability constants of the complex species¹⁻¹⁰.

As far as we are aware the stability constant has not been determined from the eluate of the cationic and anionic species of the migrant obtained after paper electrophoresis. In the present study, an attempt has been made to determine the equilibrium constant of the Fe(III)-formate system by paper electrophoresis.

Experimental

Preparation of migrant solution: $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.0100 g) was dissolved in 30 ml water with addition of a few drops of hydrochloric acid. The solution was filtered and the volume made up to 50 ml.

Preparation of the background electrolyte: Stock solutions of 2M formic acid, 2M sodium formate and 1M sodium nitrate were prepared. The background electrolyte consisted of a mixture containing 25 ml 2M sodium formate, 25 ml 2M formic acid and 50 ml 1M sodium nitrate per 100 ml solution. Sodium nitrate was used to attain the desired ionic strength. Formate concentration was fixed, ionic strength was 1.0 and the pH of the electrolyte was 3.75.

Instrument: Wieland and Fischer type horizontal set was used¹¹. The apparatus used was the cassette type and chromatograms could be run simultaneously on six paper strips. High voltage electrophoresis was carried out for 20 min at 400 volts and at 30°. Whatman No. 1 paper strips (3 × 40 cm) were used with an applied voltage gradient of 8 volt/cm.

pH measurements were made with an Elico Model L1-10 pH meter using a glass-calomel electrode assembly.

Procedure: The midpoint of each paper strip was marked and moistened with the background electrolyte and a spot of the metal solution was applied on it. The electrophoretic migration of the metal spots of different volume on the paper was observed. After electrophoresis, the spots of Fe(III) were developed with yellow ammonium sulphide. Two species were obtained in each case, one moved towards the anode and the other towards the cathode. The distances of the leading and tailing edges of the spots from the marked centre were measured. Portions of the paper containing the ions were cutout from the dried undeveloped electrophoregram after matching the positions of the ions with a developed electrophoregram subjected to identical electrophoretic conditions and environment. The paper portions containing the ions were treated with 0.8 N H_2SO_4 , to extract the ion. The extracts derived out of the strips through washings were taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume made upto the mark with 0.8 N H_2SO_4 . Similarly, blank solutions were prepared. The absorbance of the eluted iron solution was measured against these blanks at 305 m μ (Table 1).

In both the anionic and cationic species the metal ion Fe(III) present in each case was calculated

using the equation,

$$C = \frac{A}{\epsilon} = \frac{\text{Absorbance}}{\text{Extinction coefficient}}$$

where C = concentration in molarity, $\epsilon = 2180 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE 1

Migrant FeCl ₃	A	
	anionic species	cationic species
0.04 ml	0.02	0.002
	0.033	0.005
	0.021	0.002
0.08 ml	0.062	0.01
	0.064	0.01
	0.058	0.01
0.12 ml	0.210	0.017
	0.088	0.015

With these concentrations of anionic and cationic species the equilibrium constant K was calculated in each case using the equation

$$K = \frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HCOO}^-]^6}$$

The equilibrium constant K and its logarithm are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Migrant FeCl ₃	K	log K	Mean log K	log K from literature (e.m.f. method)
0.04 ml	640	2.81	2.83	3.1
	704	2.85		
	672	2.83		
0.08 ml	640	2.81	2.83	3.1
	661	2.82		
	619	2.79		
0.12 ml	790	2.90	2.80	
	625	2.80		

Discussion

In the presence of an excess of formate ion, the positive metal ion is complexed to form $[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}$ when the background electrolytes used are 25 ml 2M HCOONa, 1-15 ml 2M HCOOH, 50 ml 1M NaNO₃ and 24-10 ml water at the pH range 5.15 to 3.97.

But when the background electrolyte used is 25 ml 2M HCOONa, 25 ml 2M HCOOH, 50 ml 1M NaNO₃ at pH 3.75, the positive metal ion forms both the anionic and cationic species.

Electrophoretic study reports that most of the metal ion is complexed to form $[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}$ and a trace amount of metal ion moves as a simple cation. So there must exist an equilibrium

$$K = \frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HCOO}^-]^6}$$

where K is the equilibrium constant.

Conclusion: Paper electrophoresis technique is limited to charged species, and the precision of the method is not as high as that of other physicochemi-

cal methods. Nevertheless, it is of interest in the metal-ligand system in solution since complex formation is widely used in effecting separations of metal ions.

Acknowledgement

The authors record their sincere thanks to Professor N. N. Ghosh, Pure Chemistry Department, Calcutta University for valuable suggestions and to Dr. G. N. Mukherjee, Pure Chemistry Department, Calcutta University for encouragement.

References

1. J. BIERNAT, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1964, 38, 343.
2. V. JOKL, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1964, 14, 71.
3. B. HURNIK, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1965, 39, 137.
4. J. KOZAK, *Acta Fac. Rerum Natur. Univ. Comenianae Chem.*, 1971, 23.
5. H. KOCH and M. IOVCHEV, *Isotopenpraxis*, 1971, 7, 401.
6. E. LARSEN and J. ERIKSEN, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1975, 52, 122.
7. P. C. YADAVA, A. K. GHOSH, K. L. YADAVA and A. K. DEY, Private communication.
8. G. MARCU and M. TOMUS, *Analysis*, 1972, 1, 43.
9. B. KOZJAK, Z. MARINIC, Z. KONARD, L. MUSANT MARAZOVIC and Z. PUCAR, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1977, 132, 323.
- 10a. CZAKIS SULKOWSKA, *Zesz. Nauk, Politech. Lodz. Chem.*, 1965, 23.
- 10b. P. C. YADAVA, A. K. GHOSE, K. L. YADAVA and A. K. DEY, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1976, 119, 563.
11. T. WIELAND and E. FISCHER, *Naturwiss.*, 1948, 35, 29.
12. R. H. SCHULER and A. O. ALLEN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, 24, 56.

Relative Stability of Formate Complexes by Paper Electrophoresis

H. G. MUKHERJEE and (Miss) ALOKA DEBI

Pure Chemistry Department, University College of Science,
Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 30 March 1981, revised 23 November, 1981,
accepted 11 March 1982

STUDIES on the relative stabilities of various inorganic compounds have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵. While the oxalate, citrate, tartrate and malate complexes have been investigated, none of these studies relates to the relative stability of the formate complexes. It was therefore decided to study the relative stability of formate complexes of Fe(III), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) by paper electrophoresis.

Experimental

Migrants: 2% solution of CuSO₄.5H₂O, FeCl₃.6H₂O, CoCl₂.6H₂O and NiCl₂.6H₂O were used as migrants.

Electrolytes: Stock solutions of 2M sodium formate, 2M formic acid and 1M sodium nitrate were prepared. Sodium nitrate was used to attain the desired ionic strength.